

D4.1 Report on the methodologies and measurements explored, and guidelines including functionality, feasibility and reliability of each method for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in RI

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1 Introduction

The current report gives an overview of methodologies and measurements explored, and provides guidelines including functionality, feasibility and reliability of each method for the assessment of training initiatives and interventions in REI (research ethics and integrity). The goal of the exploration was to evaluate the measurement tools used in REI training in the past two decades, and pinpoint feasible methods for measuring effectiveness of training. While the deliverable was originally geared towards measurement of training effects in research integrity training, we have also included research ethics training, as these have sometimes been closely intertwined, and in some languages research ethics as a concept also covers integrity and these may not be strictly separated in training contents.

The report includes two approaches to the investigation of methodologies and measurements of training efficacy, namely **1) a literature review** and **2) an empirical approach to measurement testing and development**.

The literature review was conducted as part of tasks of WP1 and WP4 and includes a description of the methodology for selection of articles, pinpointing methods and measurements, and summarising of findings. The review ends with a summative table outlining all the methods and measurements with evaluations of their functionality, feasibility and reliability.

The empirical exploration involves data collected using various measurement methods in a variety of training contexts. This part of the report outlines various methods and measurements identified, designed and tested during the project. Based on this part, a toolbox of feasible measurement instruments for short-, mid- and long-term effect will be presented in D4.2.

We understand the **measurement of training effect through the learning outcomes displayed as a result of participation in training**. This means that the learning is always relative to the goals of the training. The examples of how to understand the learning taking place in REI training may be good for certain types of trainings and contexts, whereas in others they may not be feasible. Because training, its learning objectives and the pedagogical approaches vary, we have aimed to present a broad array of measurements/tools for evaluating the learning that takes place. Tools include a variety of examples ranging from self-evaluation instruments to pre-post-tests, from physiological markers to the use of authentic learning activities, from individual measurement to group learning, from micro to macro level. We have not restricted this exploration and analysis to include strictly means of measurement in a **quantitative** sense of the word but have also included **qualitative** indicators of the worth or success of training.

Short-, mid- and long-term are relative concepts. In this report, by short-term training effects we understand the learning, which is displayed during and soon after training, often evaluated based on learners' self-assessment or facilitators' evaluations during or right after the training. By mid-term we mean training effects of learning, which is displayed when the training has

ended and the learner is trying to implement the knowledge, often deducted based on tasks learners perform after the training. By long-term effects we understand the learning that is displayed months or even years after training. The longer the timeframe is, the more challenging it becomes to pinpoint what is training effect and what is development and learning in a more general sense. Long-term effects, thus, become manifestations of behaviour over time.

Feasibility is here understood as the level of effort and specialised competence or equipment that is needed to carry out the measurement or evaluation of learning. Feasibility is higher when a means of measurement or evaluation is easy and fast to implement, and lower when requiring time and specialised knowledge of the use of the method and the analysis of the results.

2 Literature review

The aim of the literature review was to identify and analyse measurement instruments and tools of assessment used to evaluate the effectiveness of REI trainings.

2.1 Method

We approached the literature review in 2 phases:

1. As agreed with the project partners, we first focused on already existing literature reviews compiled about the effectiveness of REI trainings.
2. Due to saturation of results (no new insights accumulated) and limited number of measurement instruments in the existing reviews, we conducted a separate article search to find articles with alternative measurement means of REI training effectiveness.

First, we used a set of pre-determined keywords to search databases (*Web of Science* and *Scopus*):

- research ethics * (academic) (research) integrity
- training * education * course *
- (measurement of) training effect * evaluation of training * assessment of learning

To make sure the studies were empirical, we also checked the method: qualitative * quantitative * mixed methods. We included studies from the past 10 years for review papers, but individual papers were also older.

The results from the *Web of Science* provided 124 search results, 11 review papers were relevant for the current review, 6 individual articles also provided relevant information. The results from *Scopus* provided 21 results (we limited the medical papers by ticking a limitation box as *Web of Science* already covered that), only one paper qualified as a review, 2 individual articles were added. We also used snowballing by using references of already found review papers and our own previous reference lists. Please see the PRISMA flow diagram (Page et al., 2020) for search details (Figure 1).

Figure 1: PRISMA flow chart over review process.

We started the literature review by compiling an Excel table with 2 sheets (link here: [Literature review.xlsx](#)): one for literature reviews and the other for individual articles. The literature review sheet contained 18 entries with 14 review papers (7 of which have overlapping samples) where more than 685 ethics training courses have been evaluated. There are also 3 overview papers and one method development paper (relevant for effectiveness evaluation). The individual article sheet contains 30 entries with specific training formats and measures.

2.2 Results

The **review studies** gave an overview of different training formats and evaluation tools that were used for measuring effectiveness of the trainings (summarised in Table 1). Nine of the literature reviews used quantitative or mixed methods, while seven opted for qualitative analysis (in 2 overview papers method was not specified). Disciplines covered were sciences, business, engineering, medicine, and social sciences. Context was mostly higher education (HE) where trainings were provided to students as well as researchers/academics. One article also included ethics training for school students, and one had both public and private sector covered. The findings mostly focused on outlining which training formats were effective. While active interventions seemed to be more effective, no one format was considered significantly better.

The measurement tools were:

- Self-assessment - participant reactions e.g., affective reactions toward training, participants' experiences of the relevance of the of training, difficulty of materials (Steele et al., 2016 lists 175 trainings, Stoesz & Yudintseva, 2018 list 11 trainings out of 21 that utilised self-assessment, content not specified);

- Pre-post-tests, with or without control groups – tests usually measure moral reasoning (e.g., with the Defining Issues Test, DIT), knowledge, ethical awareness and decision making (Steele et al., 2016) (Watts et al., 2017a – the base for several review papers, lists 124 trainings, Katsarov et al., 2021 outline 30 trainings, Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018 list 5 trainings out of 21);
- Post-tests, with or without control groups (Watts et al., 2017a lists 26 trainings, Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018 outline 7 studies out of 21);
- Cohen's d (difference between pre and post-tests for some studies; for some studies it contained other criteria) - this was calculated by the literature review authors (8 review papers utilised this criterion);
- One review outlined qualitative measurement methods used for REI training evaluation, namely grounded theory and general thematic analysis (Watts et al., 2017b).

As training formats were different and different measuring tools were used as pre-post-tests, the limitations were mostly outlined as:

1. extensive missing data (Watts et al., 2017a and the reviews utilising the sample of this study)
2. heterogeneity of trainings and evaluation tools (Kreismann & Talaulicar, 2021; Maesschalck & De Schrijver, 2015)
3. sometimes small sample sizes restricting the use of methods for calculating statistical inference (Marusic et al., 2016; Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018; Katsarov et al., 2021)
4. small sample sizes for qualitative analysis methods (Watts et al., 2017b).

Saturation of measurement tools was reached quickly, after reading a couple of review articles no new measurement tools were identified. The reason might be that the most prevalent measures are quantitative, and they are easy to apply (only 1 review outlined qualitative methods of 24 trainings – Watts et al., 2017b). Still, as the goals of trainings differ, different tests are used to measure those goals, comparisons become almost impossible.

Based on the analysis of reviews on training effects, we conclude that self-assessment is one of the most prevalent means to measure effectiveness of REI training. Self-assessment (or self-report of reactions to trainings) mostly focused on self-reported confidence in identifying and tackling REI issues better in the future, having learned something new, improved understanding, and having overall positive/negative feelings about the training (e.g., Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018; Steele et al., 2016). According to Steele et al. (2016), almost 30% of courses use this measure.

The second most frequently used method for assessing training effect was a moral reasoning test (various versions of Defining Issues Test - DIT). These were used in 15% of the studies included in one of the reviews (Steele et al., 2016). Ethical decision-making (at 11%), knowledge

about regulations (at about 10%) and metacognitive strategies (like perspective taking, sense-making, forecasting) (also at around 10%) followed (Steele et al., 2016). Still, as pointed out by the authors (Steele et al., 2016) there were differences between disciplines; e.g., in business moral reasoning was most popular (at 36%) followed by attitudes (prestige, materialism, social responsibility, etc.) (at 14 %) and self-assessment (reactions) (at 13%), while in science and engineering moral reasoning was used 27% of the time followed by self-assessment (reactions) (at about 20%) and measuring knowledge of regulations (at 16%).

Qualitative measures of effectiveness are scarce and the only effectiveness analysis methods were grounded theory and general thematic analysis (Watts et al., 2017b). Also, triangulation and using multiple measurement points was rare, used only in 6 studies (Watts et al., 2017a).

It seems that the measures utilised are simple to use and implement, also results do not need time-consuming analysis (e.g., in case of multiple-choice pre-post-test, the results can be automatically compiled) or require relatively non-time-consuming input in the analysis phase.

Single studies were consulted next. The individual paper list has 30 entries, out of which 7 articles describe a tool development (Bebeau et al., 1985; Rest et al., 1999; Clarkeburn, 2022; Chertok et al., 2013; Vynckier et al., 2015; Tammeleht et al., 2019; Zollisch et al., 2021). Six did not add new measurement tools or were not empirical.

In addition to developing new training formats, also tool development articles were included (7), most of them used quantitative analysis methods (to validate the tool), some used mixed methods. The tools included:

- DIT – Defining Issues Test – dilemmas followed by 12 potential ethical questions about the dilemma, the questions must be rated and ranked (Rest et al., 1999)
- TESS - Test for Ethical Sensitivity in Sciences – cases of various scientific situations, students write a response which is evaluated by the facilitator (Clarkeburn, 2002)
- DEST – Dental Ethical Sensitivity Test – students respond to dilemmas, their relative sensitivity is evaluated based on a score (Bebeau et al., 1985)
- SOLKA - Survey of Online Learning Knowledge and Attitudes – used as a pre-post test to measure knowledge and attitudes on ethical topics/actions by choosing whether it is permissible or not/dishonest or not (Chertok et al., 2014)
- P2I - P2I questionnaire, designed as a four-tier test and based on the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity; participants choose a (scientific) practice to address an issue, justify their decision, and describe how confident they are with their decisions (Zollitsch et al., 2021)
- ECAG – Ethical Case Assessment Grid, an evaluation tool based on the SOLO taxonomy to help facilitators of REI trainings evaluate the level of understanding of learners while dealing with cases (Tammeleht et al., 2019)

- EDM – Ethical Decision-Making test that presents a dilemma and provides possible courses of action out of which some are ethically valid, and some are not (designed by Mumford, described in McIntosh et al., 2018)
- SPEEES - Students' Perceived Effectiveness of Ethics Education Scale – the survey collects participants' perceptions on teaching methods, ethical content, and overall effectiveness of ethics course on a 4-point Likert scale (Vynckier et al., 2015).

Articles focused on effectiveness of REI training (16) used mostly qualitative approaches (7), 2 used quantitative methods and 6 used mixed methods (one was a descriptive paper).

While the developed tools were mostly used pre and post intervention (with/without control groups) and the results were compared, there were other measures added to evaluate the learning process or student progress. Some examples are:

- learning logs (Clarkeburn et al., 2002)
- audio-recording of group sessions (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2020, 2022; Burr & King, 2012; Buedo et al., 2023)
- group (e-)portfolios/group reports (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2022)
- student classwork (Bagdasarov et al., 2012)
- self-reported measures including satisfaction, engagement and own assessment of reaching the learning goals (Löfström, 2016; Clarkeburn et al., 2002)
- vignettes (Rissanen & Löfström, 2014)
- domain-specific and domain-transcending statements with a possibility to provide additional information (Löfström, 2012)
- think-aloud protocols (Brock et al., 2008)
- research proposals/seminar reports (Burr & King, 2012; Wada et al., 2013)

Furthermore, Burr and King (2012) indicated that the trained students' research proposals became substantially better than those of the students' who had not received the training, but this analysis was not included as an effectiveness measure. Wada et al., (2013) did use the seminar reports compiled a semester after the REI training in the effectiveness measure in an effort to longitudinally assess training outcomes. Generally, studies did not address changes in behaviour, however, these studies acknowledged that outcomes produced some time after the training may come the closest to a behavioural dimension. This is highly relevant as capturing the behavioural dimension of ethics and integrity, that is, how people actually act, is challenging.

As tools identified in single studies were analysed qualitatively or with mixed methods, one of the obvious limitations is the workload of facilitators. It takes time and effort to provide evaluation and feedback to the learners. In addition, occasionally the sample sizes were small, and interventions lasted for a very short time.

Eight of the articles (Clarkeburn et al., 2022; Brock et al., 2008; Burr & King, 2012; Wada et al., 2013; McIntosh et al., 2018 Tammeleht et al., 2019; 2022; Buedo et al., 2023) described multiple points of measurement to make a decision of the learning process/outcomes (and effectiveness

of the training). For instance, combining student work with self-assessment or audio-recording and follow up tasks. It has been pointed out that combining facilitator's and learner's evaluation of the achieved levels provide a more holistic view of what was learned (Tammeleht et al., 2022). Also, Burr and King's (2012) indication (even though it was not analysed formally) of comparing other tasks by students who had participated in trainings may provide hints of the effectiveness of the intervention.

It seems that the tests designed for ethics trainings (like DIT, EDM), cannot be universally implemented to all REI trainings (e.g. not being openly available), or they have not been implemented widely enough to conclude on their usefulness (like DEST, TESS).

2.3 Summary

We summarise the results of the literature review along the following questions:

- What is the state-of-the-art knowledge on this topic?
- What are challenges / trends / opportunities?
- What potential research gaps are there?

What is the state-of-the-art knowledge?

- While active interventions seemed to be more effective, no one format was considered significantly better.
- **Self-assessment** is one of the most prevalent means to measure effectiveness of REI training. The second most frequently used method for assessing training effect was a **moral reasoning test**.
- While the developed tools were mostly used pre and post intervention (with/without control groups) and the results were compared, there were generally other measures added to evaluate the learning process or student progress.
- It seems that the tests designed for ethics trainings (like DIT, DEST, TESS) cannot be universally implemented to all REI trainings due to very different formats of training and/or availability of tests.
- While review papers outlined that the most used and likely most feasible measures were self-assessment measuring learner reactions, and pre-post-tests measuring knowledge and skills learned, individual papers also outlined other, qualitative possibilities to monitor the learning progress, and through that assess the effectiveness of training, that is, establishing whether learners learn as a result of the training.

What are challenges / trends / opportunities?

Challenges in assessing training effectiveness include:

- Research results are limited through extensive missing data, heterogeneity of trainings and evaluation tools, short interventions not allowing sufficient time to induce change or development, and small sample sizes.
- As the goals of trainings differ, different tests are used to measure those goals, making comparisons difficult.

- Measurements take a lot of time and labour to assess and analyse, especially if the data are qualitative and learners receive feedback on their learning and development.

Trends and opportunities in assessing training effectiveness include:

- Combining facilitator's and learner's evaluation of the achieved levels provide a more holistic view of what was learned
- There is a trend to triangulate measurements to gain a holistic view of learning and development of the understanding of RE/RI.

What potential research gaps are there in assessing training effectiveness?

- Qualitative measures of effectiveness are scarce. While most prevalent measures are quantitative, there is a need to also include and develop qualitative approaches to research REI learning and development.
- There is also a need to utilise method triangulation and multiple measurement points.
- While measuring participants' reactions and knowledge/skill is relatively easy to organise, measuring behaviour and results is more difficult. Measures for behavioural change are much scarcer than attitude or perception measures. Outcomes produced some time after the training may come the closest to measuring a behavioural dimension, i.e., they may serve as displays of ethical planning in the absence of actual observations of how people function in everyday research situations. Utilising such displays as research data is still scarce.

Table 1 in section 2.4 outlines the measurement tools explored, indicates Kirkpatrick's measurement level (based on Praslova, 2010, 1 – learner reactions; 2 – learning content and learning process; 3 – behaviour and practices; 4 – institutional/societal impact), evaluates the tools' functionality, feasibility (scale/ inter-disciplinary/ facilitator workload), reliability/ comparability, influence of AI to the tool's applicability (i.e. the possibility of AI tools being used by learners to manipulate the results), and assesses short-, mid- and long-term effects of the training. Details and recommendations are outlined in section 5.

2.4 Summarising table of measurements from the literature review

Table 1. Explored methodologies and measurements for REI training effectiveness

Measurement/ instrument	Kirkpatrick's measurement level	Functionality	Feasibility (large scale/ inter- disciplinary/ facilitator workload)	Reliability/ comparability	Influence of AI	Short/ mid/ long term effects
DIT – Defining Issues Test (Rest et al., 1999)	2 (3)	dilemmas followed by 12 potential ethical questions about the dilemma, the questions must be rated and ranked	Problematic to use large-scale – big workload, analysis will cost money (analysis criteria not available, USA university provides the analysis, European data protection issues). But is quite general for interdisciplinary use.	Training courses that use DIT can be compared. Reliable as it has been developed as part of robust research, has been tested a lot.	Cannot probably be done with the help of AI.	Mid/long. Too substantial for measuring short-term training effects
TESS - Test for Ethical Sensitivity in Sciences (Clarkeburn, 2002)	2	cases of various scientific situations, students write a response which is evaluated by the facilitator	Possible to use large- scale (easy to set up), but involves a lot of work from the facilitator, criteria for evaluation not available, possibly should be designed by the facilitator. Cases	Comparable in contexts where TESS is in use, student progress can be measured if TESS is used several times. Reliable as the test is research based.	Theoretically the case can be inserted into generative AI tool and can be asked to be commented. Still, our test so far indicate that	Mid-term

			can be selected based on disciplines or be general.		the level of the AI response is relatively limited.	
DEST – Dental Ethical Sensitivity Test (Bebeau et al., 1985)	2	students respond to dilemmas (often they listen to recordings of situations), their relative sensitivity is evaluated based on a score (based on transcribed data)	The test has been designed for dental students, but the format may be usable in different disciplines. Implementation may be challenging (if using audio-recordings) and evaluation takes time and several raters. Not feasible for large-scale use.	Reliable as it is research-based and in use in dentistry; comparable to other DEST formats.	If listening to the situation and responding happens on the spot, then AI use is not possible.	Mid-term use likely possible
SOLKA - Survey of Online Learning Knowledge and Attitudes (Chertok et al., 2014)	2	used as a pre-post test to measure knowledge and attitudes on ethical topics/actions by choosing whether it is permissible or not/dishonest or not	Large-scale use possible, can be implemented pre and post course to evaluate learned content and attitudes (statistical analysis). May provide limited information about the learning process.	Reliable as it is research-based, provides statistics of improvement scores – participant improvement can be measured.	Probably not feasible to use AI.	Short/mid-term
P2I questionnaire (Zollitsch et al., 2021)	3	designed as a four-tier test and based on the European	A standardised measurement for any training, topics can be	Development and initial testing is reliable, but more	AI use not feasible.	short/mid-term

		Code of Conduct for Research Integrity; participants choose a (scientific) practice to address an issue, justify their decision, and describe how confident they are with their decisions	chosen, follow ECoC. Quite easy to implement, also large-scale as includes multiple-choice answers. Results in the form of scores (statistical analysis possible), interpretation may require prior training.	testing and large-scale use might be needed. Courses that use the questionnaire can be compared.		
ECAG - Ethical Case Assessment Grid, (Tammeleht et al., 2019)	2	an evaluation tool based on the SOLO taxonomy to help facilitators of REI trainings evaluate the level of understanding of learners while dealing with cases	Getting to know the SOLO taxonomy requires some training, but when facilitator is familiar with it, evaluation is fast. Can be used to evaluate individuals or groups, in the classroom or based on written reports. Takes facilitator time, but not too much. Suitable for small to mid-sized groups and for evaluating specific learning tasks.	Research-based taxonomy in the background and has been tested. Results help compare students' progress, groups, courses, to self-evaluation – as long as SOLO is used consistently.	AI use may be possible, but has not been tested.	short/mid

EDM – Ethical Decision-Making test (designed by Mumford, described in McIntosh et al., 2018)	2/3	a test that presents a dilemma and provides possible courses of action out of which some are ethically valid, and some are not	Usually administered as a pre- and post-test. Consists of a series of discipline-specific scenarios followed by multiple choice questions. The test takes about 45 minutes. Evaluation criteria not openly available (offered for money by a US university) but can probably be developed by facilitators.	Reliable as it is research-based; comparable if used as pre-post-test (individual development).	AI use possible but perhaps not feasible	short/mid
SPEEES - Students' Perceived Effectiveness of Ethics Education Scale (Vynckier et al., 2015).	1	The survey collects participants' perceptions on teaching methods, ethical content and overall effectiveness of ethics course on a 4-point Likert scale	An instrument to measure participants perceived effectiveness of the course – could be implemented into various courses. Not openly available, no evaluation criteria available.	Has been tested in nursing education context and not on large scales, is a reliable and valid instrument.	Evaluation criteria not available.	short/mid-term
Measurement for domain- transcending and domain-specific	2 (3)	Excerpts from research proposals, and also concept	The part regarding concept understanding can be analysed using	Research-based, but used with limited samples.	AI could be used in the part on concept	short/mid/long term

ethical awareness (Löfström, 2012)		recognition and understanding measuring domain-specific and domain-general RE/RI knowledge. Can be combined with measures of ethical climate and empathy.	the SOLO Taxonomy, but requires input from the facilitator, which makes it not feasible in large-scale context. The excerpts from research proposals can be assessed relatively fast, and this part is better suited also for large-scale use.		recognition. The multiple choice-type of set up of the research excerpt proposal part is less manipulatable with AI.	
Vignettes (Rissanen & Löfström, 2014; partly based on Zuccherò, 2008)	2 (3)	Vignettes measure ethical sensitivity. Can be combined with measures of empathy and socialisation.	Suitable for small to mid-sized groups Large-scale not feasible, as evaluation requires human input. Can be used in various disciplines.	Research-based, but used with limited samples.	AI could be used to write the text.	short /mid/long term
Learning logs (Clarkeburn et al., 2002)	2	Students write learning logs on given topics and facilitator evaluates them.	Can be applicable large-scale, especially useful with online learning environments. But takes time for the facilitator to evaluate then, also criteria for evaluation not available.	Has been used but no detailed research has been done on reliability. Helps monitor the individual's development and depending on criteria, makes	AI could be used to write the text.	mid-term

				comparisons between individuals possible.		
Audio-recording of group sessions (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2020, 2022; Burr & King, 2012; Buedo et al., 2023)	2	group discussions are audio-recorded for later use – evaluating the learning process	May not be usable large-scale as would take a long time to re-listen to all the group discussions, extra workload for facilitators; could be used in interdisciplinary settings.	Has been used in REI settings and has proven valid. If a common taxonomy is used, then comparisons could be possible.	We have not tested AI to evaluate recordings. Inserting people's personal data into AI may pose data management risks.	Provides information on short-term progress, but in the long run makes long-term monitoring of development possible.
Group (e)portfolios/ group reports (Tammeleht et al., 2019, 2022)	2	groups take notes during group-work, the report/portfolio helps anchor the discussion and provides suitable scaffolding	Easy to set up and later evaluate, makes also comparisons possible; can be used in interdisciplinary settings. For experienced facilitators does not take very much time to evaluate the content.	If the group report/portfolio has been set up based on a scaffolding framework and a common taxonomy is used for evaluation, then comparisons are possible and reliable.	AI can be used to write the text. The group could be asked to use one computer per team or fill in the report in writing by hand.	mid term
Student class-work (Bagdasarov et al., 2012)	2	information on various tasks students engage in	May not be feasible for large-scale data collection, but would	Would provide reliable information of the learning	Classwork can be completed with the use of	mid term

		during the training are collected (tests, reports, oral presentations, group discussions)	provide a holistic picture of the learning process. Will take time for the facilitator to go over all the items.	process that is also comparable.	AI, but may not be applicable to all tasks.	
Self-reported measures including satisfaction, engagement and own assessment of reaching the learning goals (Löfström, 2016; Clarkeburn et al., 2002)	1	learners are asked to evaluate their own engagement and progress, also are asked how satisfied they were with the training.	Learners' self-evaluation of their engagement, satisfaction and progress is a common and feasible way to collect information on short-term impact, can be used in interdisciplinary settings.	If the tool for self-evaluation is research based, then comparisons can be made and results are reliable. Courses can be compared if the same tool is used for self-report.	AI could be used but perhaps not feasible as usually the measurement tools are rather short and ask for personal reflection.	shot-term
Think-aloud protocols (Brock et al., 2008)	2	Learner's competence development is evaluated based on the (recorded) oral answers to topics/questions.	If the answers are not recorded, it takes one facilitator to evaluate one response (similar to oral exams), so may not be feasible in large scale. Recordings can be evaluated later, but it will take considerable time. Can be used in various disciplines.	Is reliable and comparable if the same format is used.	If the evaluation is done on the spot based on the oral answer, AI will probably not be used.	short/mid

Research proposals/ seminar reports (Burr & King, 2012; Wada et al., 2013)	3	Learners' who have participated in REI training provide their other work (usually created in other courses or contexts) to display their REI competencies.	It would be feasible to collect other forms of proof of learners' competencies (as they do not have to do extra work), but evaluation them takes time. Could be done in various disciplines.	Reliable for of evaluation (there are research-based examples) and comparable (if learners submit comparable material).	AI could be used to complete those tasks.	Mid/long term
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3 Empirical evidence of possible measures of training effects collected in BEYOND

This section will give an overview of measurement tools WP4 has collected evidence on in the past 2 years. Most of the measurement techniques would help evaluate the four variables: reactions (participants' self-assessment), learning (knowledge, content), behaviour (acting in the research community) and results (e.g. institutional outcomes) (Praslova, 2010 based on Kirkpatrick's framework dating back to 1959).

For all the tools we have collected evidence of their usability in REI training context. Evidence came in different formats (see more details in chapters below and in included references) and was analysed mostly qualitatively, but occasionally mixed methods were utilised.

The tools that are feasible to implement for measuring short-, mid- and long-term impact of REI training identified from the literature review as well as research conducted during the BEYOND project will be outlined in Deliverable 2 of WP4.

3.1 Self-reflection

Previous studies indicate (Steele et al., 2016; Stoesz & Yuditseva, 2018; Turner et al., 2018) that self-assessment or collecting participant reactions is used the most in evaluating training effectiveness. Our goal was to develop a measurement tool based on self-report which is trustworthy and feasible and could be used in long-term perspective and follow-up settings. The self-reflection tool helps learners monitor their learning process as well as provides important insights about the uptake of REI course content to facilitators. A detailed description of the tool development and the analysis of the accuracy of the collected data has been provided in Tammeleht and Löfström (2023). The results from testing iterations show that most learners can quite accurately evaluate their level of understanding in the context of research ethics and integrity and repeated reflection appears to improve accuracy of self-reflection (Tammeleht & Löfström, 2023). The tool is suitable for evaluation of short-term outcomes of training, and conclusions on training impact on researcher behaviour cannot be made. The tool is currently being developed into an app.

3.2 Learning diaries

In order to monitor how ethics competencies (e.g. awareness and recognition of ethical principles, utilising ethical analysis, reflecting on ethical cases, etc.) develop during the training session and also see if the competencies are retained over a longer period of time reflective learning diaries were used to monitor the development of REI competencies as well as effectiveness of the training in the long term. Reflection is a crucial part of ethics education as it supports the development of ethical sensitivity and ethical decision-making (Mustajoki and Mustajoki 2017; Löfström and Tammeleht 2023). Written reflection tasks may provide good results as writing offers a chance to pause and have an inner dialogue with oneself.

Still, the question is – how to evaluate diary entries? As measurement criteria the SOLO taxonomy (Biggs, 1999) as well as Mezirov’s levels of reflection (Kember et al., 1999; see also Bell et al., 2011; Kember et al., 2000; Kember et al., 2008) can be used to evaluate the level of understanding and reflection of REI topics in the diaries. As a result of the analysis (Tammeleht, Löfström & Rajando, 2024), it can be said that learning diaries can be used as a didactical but also a measurement tool: learning diaries can be used to support learners in making connections between various content criteria and enhance reflection, which is vital in ethical decision-making. Results indicated that submitting learning diaries in the forum format (learners can read and respond to each other’s submissions) supports displaying content knowledge on high levels of reflection and understanding. In addition, submitting learning diaries during a longer period and making repeated submissions can improve reflection and understanding of REI as well as monitor the retention of those competencies. (Tammeleht, Löfström & Rajando, 2024)

3.3 Eye-tracking

Research on visual attention in the context of moral judgment is scarce. A study by Zarkadi and Schnall (2013) indicated a connection between visual pattern and activating dichotomous thinking resulting in the judgement of a moral dilemma in a polarized way. Visual attention, while underexplored in this context, may have the potential of revealing new insights about how learners process information for moral judgment in learning situations. Gaze-tracking collects a very large number of data points and thus allows within-person comparisons through focusing on events that are similar and frequent. This enables the analysis of how an individual (re)acts across these situations.

The data can be viewed for example through heat maps. To facilitate the analysis, we have used visual markers (QR codes) to synchronise the data. Still, the analysis is time-consuming and would not be usable for large-scale measurement of learning. However, potentially it opens up new insights on collaborative and case-based REI learning, which have been identified as the state-of-the-art pedagogy in REI (see Löfström & Tammeleht, 2023).

While eye-tracking is a safe and non-invasive research method, ethical issues in employing eye-tracking have been identified (Hannula et al., 2022) including the bodily experience (see also Duru, 2018) of wearing mobile camera devices, in this case, eye-tracking glasses. In addition, we have identified in the BEYOND exploration calibration difficulties when a participant is on a certain kind of medication or when the pupil colour is very dark. Thus, medical information may emerge in the calibration situation even though this is not data sought after and is not used as research data. The issue of pupil colour could raise awareness of racial aspects, and even though the research setting is non-racial and non-discriminatory, a participant could potentially feel intimidation because of the technological challenges in connection to their external characteristics such as dark pupil colour.

3.4 Empathy measurement

Emotional engagement has been identified as a criterion of effective ethics education already three decades ago (see Warren, 1995). It has been argued that using live cases in ethics education is beneficial as these promote the emotional connection of the topic in the learner. More precisely, taking and defending a position has been identified as a means to achieve emotion-related goals in ethics teaching (McWilliams & Nahavandi, 2006). Emotivist models (Haidt 2001; Leffel et al., 2015; Mumford et al., 2008) complement the idea that ethical decision-making is a rational and cognitive process. According to these models, reasoning does not take place in an emotional vacuum, on the contrary, intuition and emotion are central in ethical decision-making. The question then is, what role do emotions play?

Scholars have suggested empathy to be a vital component of ethical decision-making (cf. Bebeau, Rest & Narvaez, 1999; Butterfield, Treviño, & Weaver, 2000; Weaver, 2007). Empathy has been defined mainly as an affective dimension involving an ability to imagine others' feelings, or own feelings in a similar situation, which helps responding ethically to others (Hoffman, 2000, p. 4) and engage in responsible action (Claypool & Molnar, 2011).

However, empathy has also been described as involving perspective taking (a cognitive dimension) in addition to emotional contagion (an affective dimension) (Sparks & Hunt, 1998). The Empathy scales including four items for both subscales, developed by Sparks and Hunt (1998) have been adapted to the context of research ethics context by Löffström (2012). While the initial instrument was developed for a marketing ethics context, its adaptation worked reasonably well in a research ethics context. The study (Löffström, 2012) indicated a correlation between perspective taking correlating and ethical awareness, while another study did not bring forth relationships between empathy and awareness of ethical issues in research (Rissanen & Löffström, 2014). Both studies were conducted with student samples.

In the context of research ethics and integrity training it may be difficult to collect sufficiently large data sets to be able to perform meaningful statistical analyses. However, the empathy scales can work to trigger self-reflection and a discussion around empathy in ethical decision-making. Recognising empathy as resource for ethical decision-making may fit well with other reflective approaches in training and be a plausible measure of training effectiveness when learning objectives are related to improving self-understanding in ethical decision-making in research contexts.

As part of BEYOND activities we collaborated with WP3 and tested an empathy measurement tool with students who received a short training with more emotion-triggering content and traditional training. The results showed no significant differences between the two training groups suggesting that longer training formats may be needed for impact on empathy. However, for longer REI training with learning objectives related to fostering empathy, existing survey-type empathy scales may be meaningful as well as feasible.

3.5 National surveys

BEYOND has explored what can be learned from national integrity surveys and barometers about REI training effect (Tammeleht et al., submitted). While the surveys may not address training directly, they can be used as macro-level long-term reflections of the state of REI in a given context, and as such they may also be reflections of whether training efforts, in a broad sense, have been efficient. As the evaluation of training effect cannot be tied to specific training at this macro-level, it may provide indications of the extent of challenges, which could have or can be alleviated through training, and point a direction of training needs.

The well-being and integrity of research community relates to leadership which means anticipating challenges and problems, perceiving them accurately and being ready to provide viable solutions or support others in the solving. REI leadership means leadership on every level in the HE institution including supervisors, programme leaders, research team leaders, department heads to deans and rectors. The REI leadership framework combines ethical, authentic and transcendental leadership (Tammeleht et al., 2022). Similarly, this idea is transferable to other types of research-performing organisations as well.

To explore this idea, BEYOND partners carried out a meta-analysis for a cross-case study of five countries: Estonia, Finland, Norway, France and the Netherlands. We identified published reports or articles of national REI surveys of the five partner countries. In this exploration we focused specifically on REI leadership with the identification of training needs and catering for the prerequisites for researchers' competence development being key tasks of leadership. Based on the following leadership principles we conducted deductive thematic analysis:

- researchers' needs
- developing the community
- leaders' personal competencies, and
- encouraging an open research culture.

The analysis showed that it is helpful to set indicators like the ones mentioned above, in order to focus the analysis. Based on the results, we identified aspects in the national surveys/barometers pertaining to training or training needs. Statistics in national surveys provides information about availability and attendance of REI training. Qualitative analysis of the leadership level indicated aspects that require attention on the institutional or societal level.

3.6 Group reports/portfolios

Group reports or (e-)portfolios are examples of authentic learning tasks that offer insight into the learning processes of groups (as opposed to individuals) have been utilised during trainings in the past few years (e.g. with the resource: <https://en.researchethicscompass.net/>). Prior research has confirmed (Tammeleht et al., 2019; 2022) that using 'the epistemic artefacts' in the form of group reports reflect the advancement of knowledge and co-creation of knowledge. In addition, a written collaborative 'artefact' with facilitator-induced guidelines provides structural scaffolding like decomposing the task, asking leading questions, redirecting learners, goal

orientation and highlighting important aspects (Tammeleht et al., 2020). Thus, requesting a written group report during the training may act as a didactical as well as a measurement tool. A ready template may be helpful in pinpointing themes for the group, or the aspects a portfolio should preferably cover. After/during the training the facilitator can monitor the advancement of ethics competencies of learners based on the report.

3.7 The use of authentic learning tasks in large-scale interdisciplinary online REI training

In this section we discuss a means to evaluate the effectiveness of large-scale REI training. To increase feasibility, we have explored how authentic learning tasks and activities can be used as indicators of training effectiveness. We see much potential in the utilisation of authentic tasks and activities, as these accumulate, and should be reflections of the materialisation of learning objectives.

To make this exploration more tangible, we use a large, interdisciplinary online training course for doctoral students as an example. The course is mandatory for all doctoral students at the University of Helsinki and thus it is strongly interdisciplinary since it invites doctoral students from each Faculty and Doctoral programme of the University. There are about 400 participants each semester. Designing and assessing a large-scale online course takes a lot of planning. The described course is a one-month online course on key issues of research ethics, and it is set up in the Moodle platform.

The course includes a series of online lecture videos and written texts (including links to further online resources) on each topic, followed by Quizzes or Reflective Activities about the topic in question (Assessment 5). Each topic also includes Case Studies, research ethics cases, that students discuss in groups of 5 (Assessment 3). After the first week students submit their first essay (approx. 2 pages) in which they describe the ethical questions and challenges of their own research (Assessment 1). These essays are then distributed among the students so that each gets one essay from a student of their own discipline (or close to it) and one from any other discipline. During the second week students write short peer reviews of these essays (Assessment 2). In the final essay (again approx. 2 p.) in the end of the course students are asked to consider ethics of their own research again by reflecting the comments they have received in peer reviews. They should also show that they are now able to recognize ethical issues at each stage of their research (planning, conducting, publishing, communication) (Assessment 4). In this sense, even though it is an online course, it is a kind of application of flipped learning (DeLozier & Rhodes 2017; Tucker 2012). In the course, students familiarize themselves with the course's online materials and lectures on different areas of research ethics and apply this in the Assessments. Evaluation is designed as following:

During the course:

- Self-evaluation through Reflective Activities and Quizzes
- Peer review of the 1st essays

- Peer evaluation in Group Discussions about the Case Studies

At the end of the course:

- Self-evaluation: responding to the peer reviews and reflecting on one’s development needs
- Teacher evaluates the final, 2nd essay that includes topics from all modules

Figure 2 shows the modules and assessment points of the course.

Figure 2: Course structure and points of assessment.

The general pedagogical idea informing the design of the methods is that the chosen method should be aligned with required skill level of each intended learning outcome. Table 2 summarizes how the teaching methods utilised in the course relate to the intended learning outcomes of the course. For example, online lectures and following Quizzes and Reflective Activities are meant to provide students with Blooms Taxonomy’s lower order cognitive skills, such *remembering* and *understanding*, while Essays, Peer Review and Group Discussions help students in developing higher order skills, such as *applying* and *evaluating*. Since this an introductory course the higher order skills are essentially related to skills highlighted in the intended learning outcomes of doctoral programmes.

Table 2 Teaching methods and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

Course ILOs	Teaching Methods
1. Describe key ethical principles guiding scientific research and	- the online Lectures introduce the key principles and students need to describe and select them in Reflective activities and Quizzes

<p>select principles that are relevant for their own research work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in their own 1st and 2nd essay students need to show how the principles relate to their own research - in peer review exercise they need to describe whether the principles have been identified and selected by their peer students - in Case Studies students select research ethical principles to solve ethical problems
<p>2. Write ethical research plans and describe responses to ethical challenges by applying key ethical theories and approaches.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - based on online Lectures, Reflective Activities, and Group Discussions, students describe in their 1st and 2nd essay the ethical challenges of their own research and how they plan to solve these challenges.
<p>3. Identify and describe key research ethical questions at each stage of research (planning, conducting, sharing the results) and especially how they might emerge in their own research.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the online Lectures introduce the main ethical questions related to each stage and students need to show that they are able to identify them in Quizzes, Reflective Activities (e.g. by writing a Subjectivity Statement) and in their 1st and 2nd essay. - the 1st essay and peer reviewing are effective in showing to the student how well they have been able to describe the ethical questions of their research.
<p>4. Explain how the Finnish Responsible Conduct of Research guidelines are applied in their own research and how the processes for dealing with research misconduct are organised in their own research unit.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the online material is divided in sections according to the guidelines and starts with an introduction of the responsible conduct and potential misconduct. - the material includes a description of the process of dealing with misconduct - in Case Studies students need to explain in Group Discussions how to misconduct cases are dealt with - in their own 1st and 2nd essay students need to show how the guidelines apply to their own research
<p>5. Describe the rights and responsibilities of a researcher and their research community.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the online material deals with relationship bw. researcher and their research context, community, supervisor etc - students need to describe these in their Subjectivity Statement (one of the Reflective Activities), in the Group Discussion about the Case Studies and finally in their 1st and 2nd essay.

<p>6. Collaboratively discuss and solve research ethical questions over disciplinary boundaries and in multidisciplinary cooperation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the Peer Review is done to one essay from own discipline and to another from any other discipline - in Group Discussions the groups are highly multidisciplinary
<p>7. Communicate about their research ethically, but also about the ethics of their research.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the online Lecture on sharing the results and its Quizzes deal with questions of ethics of science communication - in 1st and 2nd essays students need to communicate about the ethical questions of their research to their peers - in Peer Review they give constructive feedback about the ethical questions of other students - in multidisciplinary Group Discussions they discuss constructively about research ethics

Since the intended learning outcomes of the course are essentially related to skills of a researcher, the course design supports developing and practicing of those skills. Moreover, in research ethics, the role of skills is often emphasized even more, because research ethics can well be seen as ethics of *practitioners*, who must act to solve practical problems to carry out research activity in specific circumstances. Thus, the researchers must have skills to identify potential problems, devise possible solutions, then make judgments to select a particular course of action and implement it within the context of their research practice.

The following have been identified as challenges in large-scale trainings: Students generally expect to receive feed-back on their own discipline-specific questions they have in mind and when the course material does not cover them or the peer review does not provide advice, they might lose their motivation. This is a challenge for the training effectiveness and may be reflected in the effort participants put into the training activities and tasks. To address this issue, more advanced courses are offered as part of different doctoral school programmes that are discipline specific.

Another challenge is the large student body and online teaching format. Dividing a large number of students into smaller workshops, either as face-to-face teaching or as a combination of online and face-to-face teaching (blended learning), may provide a partial solution to not being able to be properly present during the course and may increase the feasibility of using such tasks as measures of learning, and eventually training effectiveness.

3.8 Multimodal learning analytics (MMLA) tools in REI training

As part of BEYOND activities we have tested/piloted some tools for MMLA. Such tools are becoming increasingly easy to implement as measures of effectiveness during training sessions. All the described tools are research based and developed by educational researchers.

CoTrack application (<https://www.cotrack.website/en/>) monitors group dynamics and turn-taking of participants during group-work. *CoTrack* has previously been used in REI training context (see Tammeleht et al., 2022). We piloted it also with WP3 to monitor group dynamics during a discussion game on ethics (see figure 3) (Parder et al., 2024). The application provides information about group dynamics: how active were participants during group discussions and how their interaction was directed. This MMLA tool does not provide information about the degree to which training content has been learned, but if the learning objectives include engagement in dialogue (like for example the Debate and Dialogue exercise developed in the Virt2UE project) (Stolper & Inguaggiato, n.d.), then this tool can be used to capture the learning

process.

Figure 3. Piloting results with *CoTrack* (with 4 participants) (from Parder et al., 2024).

Another application that has MMLA potential in REI training context is *ProLearning* (www.prolearning.realto.ch) which collects learner responses to teacher-generated questions (yes/no or scale 0-100), asks teachers to predict the learner responses and write a short description of the learning situation. Only then can the teacher see the graph outlining learner responses (based on groups) in relation to their own predictions (see figure 4). If the teacher prediction of the performance of a group of learners is seen as the expected learning outcome, then the use of this tool can provide a measure of the alignment or discrepancy between the expected effectiveness and the learners' performance.

Figure 4. Example of *ProLearning* measurement of the same question asked 6 times.

In addition, engagement in activities may have an impact on how well people acquire competencies. For measuring engagement, an application *ForgetNot* (by EduLog) is available: <https://web.htk.tlu.ee/forgetnot>. In the application, learners can provide their feedback on three aspects of the training (see figure 5): how they were engaged in the activities (behavioural aspect of learning), how they felt (emotional aspect of learning) and how relevant the knowledge was for them (cognitive aspect of learning). All these aspects are relevant in case of successful learning. The responses accumulate based on the group and provide information to the facilitator how the training format was perceived by learners.

Figure 5. *ForgetNot* results by groups (group identifier on the left) indicating their scores (1-6) of behavioural, emotional and cognitive aspects.

The *ForgetNot* app has not been tested in REI context yet, but it includes aspects relevant for REI competence development (testing is planned for autumn 2024).

3.9 Monitoring the entire learning process and the long-term impact

One option to measure effectiveness of a learning process and outcomes is to check multiple points during the learning process and after the intervention. The literature review conducted during the project pointed out that pre- and post-testing is a common measure to evaluate training effectiveness. Still, the tests are different and may not give a full picture of what happens during the training process. We have tested collecting evidence of learner progress, e.g. learning diaries, pre and post texts, comparing texts submitted during the course and then submitted after the course has ended (e.g. RE sections in articles or dissertations for PhD students).

This kind of data collection requires some planning from the facilitator – text collection measures should be planned (a Moodle course may be convenient as all submissions by the same person will accumulate there); group size should be considered (in case of large groups

it may not be too time-consuming to keep an eye on many submissions); perhaps colleagues can collaborate to collect texts (e.g. one text collected during the course and another later during another course).

Analysis of texts collected at various points may provide insights of what the learning process was like as well as whether the competencies have been retained. This could be achieved by asking learners keep a learning diary, submitting an ethical reflection before the training, right after the training and perhaps a few months after the training. Facilitators could also analyse ethical sensitivity in texts submitted during the training and then in a text submitted as part of another course, activity (e.g. a research article, research project proposal, etc.).

Examples of monitoring retention have been reported. For example, Tammeleht, Lofström & Rajando (2024) outline that in order to measure retention of REI competencies (measured in the learning diaries during one semester of a one-year long micro-credential programme) a case study was conducted five months after finishing with learning diaries. Results indicated that participants had retained their competencies by displaying ethical principles and ethical analysis steps, learners also indicated ethical approaches they used in completing the tasks. The lowest levels of reflection or understanding were not present at all. Relatively high levels of reflection and understanding may indicate that the training had been effective.

In collaboration with WP3 we measured the effectiveness of a short intervention and compared two groups where one received a more emotionally delivered content while the other received traditional (non-emotional) delivery of training. Both groups submitted a pre-text, did a self-reflection and self-evaluation task right after the seminar and then submitted a post-text 2 months after the intervention. The results indicated that both groups benefitted for the seminar as the levels of understanding improved from pre- to post-texts. In addition, learners self-evaluated levels of understanding were retained 2 months after the intervention. There were no significant differences between the groups – both improved (which may be the impact of the facilitator), but the ‘emotional’ group displayed a higher percentage of the highest level of understanding (26%) opposed to the non-emotional group (12%) in the post-text. While the self-evaluation and textual tasks provided information about the learning and retention over time, they also provided information for training developers on the efficiency of two different training formats.

4 Conclusions and recommendations

Table 1 summarises functionality and feasibility of measures identified in the review. The table also provides an assessment of the time span for which we judge that the measure is well suited. We also present an assessment of the domain in which the measures may be best used, as well as an estimation of how the measure functions with the use of AI, that is, is the measure vulnerable to (undesirable) manipulative use or is it likely measuring learners’ learning and understanding.

Several review papers (e.g. Steele et al., 2016, Mumford et al., 2015) point out that effectiveness of REI training is most often based on four Kirkpatrick's variables (Praslova, 2010). The reviews admit that while measuring participants' reactions and knowledge/skill is relatively easy to organise, measuring behaviour and results is more difficult. Even if the measure claims to be measuring behaviour (e.g., the EDM test by Mumford et al., 2008), it still may not indicate if the person would act ethically in future situations.

This indicates that evaluating the learning and adoption of ethical competencies as a result of training could be approached as a system. Measuring reactions and knowledge as part of the training is reasonable, but to get a more holistic picture of the impact of the training as well as the environment, other measures should be designed and used to get insights into behaviour and institutional outcomes. Ethics training could be seen as one piece in the ethics infrastructure contributing to the culture of integrity, thus the evaluation should also measure the system, not only the training. If the overall goal is to have a research community where everyone will make ethically sound choices, then various measurement points should be implemented. Different measurement/evaluation instruments are needed for targeting individual and institutional outcomes and these could be aligned at least to some extent. While review papers outlined that the most used (and probably feasible) measures were self-assessment (measuring reactions) and pre-post-tests (to measure what knowledge and skills were learned), single-study reports also outlined other possibilities to monitor the learning progress. Still, single-study reports indicated that various measurements take a lot of time and labour to assess and analyse. This means, comparing effectiveness or what happens during the learning process is challenging for various formats of training. Yet, designing a measurement tool for every training format may not be feasible.

What could be asked is: what do the different training formats have in common and what is expected in all trainings? The common denominators might be compared, i.e., what aspect can always be expected to be achieved irrespective of the type or content of training? We envision these aspects to be related to deepening of understanding or engagement and commitment.

Another option would be to combine different measurement points – self-assessment and facilitator feedback as well as looking at the attitudes and behaviour traits (in tasks that display REI competencies in research community, like research proposals, ethics sections of theses, articles, etc.). Measurement may take place at different time points – during the training (learning process), right after the training – students' and facilitator's self-reports, and then later as part of another event or course where the display of REI competencies is expected (like RE section in theses and articles, research proposal, evaluation of RE situation in the department, etc.) Of course, to combine different measurement points should still have a common taxonomy or framework to make the triangulation valid. Moreover, unless the measure can be automated, the workload of facilitators should be considered. Last, there must be a rationale for measuring, i.e., what is the new knowledge and understanding the measuring or evaluation brings, and how can this insight be used to further develop initiatives in support of a culture of integrity.

We recognise that measures suited for long-term measurement are scarce, with short and mid-term use are most common. This may be due to the fact that the requirement for robustness of the measurement tool increases as time passes and a variety of variables may play a role.

Finally, measurements of learning may be subject to AI manipulation. Some of the tests or tools may be easier to manipulate than others as indicated in Table 1. Still, our testing with AI tools (e.g. ChatGTP, HuggingChat) has indicated that the responses generated by large language models tend to be rather superficial (e.g., leaving out important stakeholders/perspectives), include no reflection or affective component, base the response on some codes of conduct/guidelines (not cited) that may not be relevant for a given context, and generally barely reach a threshold level of relational understanding.

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